

Fiber Bragg gratings as strain and damage sensors for aerospace applications

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ABSTRACT: Real aerospace composite parts, like curved stiffened panels used as cowlings in Airbus aircrafts, stiffened panels and ribs, have been instrumented with standard strain gauges and FBG sensors, and submitted to mechanical tests up to failure. Besides to identify the difficulties of using fiber optics as strain sensors, artificial delaminations and flaws were introduced, in order to evaluate the ability of fiber Bragg gratings for damage detection.

Strain measurements of embedded FBGs can be compromised by spurious phenomena like birefringence promoted by residual stresses, with the subsequent spectral peak splitting, or spectral chirping caused by local non uniform strain fields. Surface bonded sensors are preferred for fabric laminates to avoid a highly distorted reflected peak. Both surface bonded or embedded sensors in case of tape laminates, showed a very good comparison or measurements from electrical and optical strain gauges.

Under static tests, fiber optic strain sensors were insensitive to damage, even in cases when sensor was located at the surface on top of the delaminated region. Practical issues, as the use of optical fiber ribbons for embedding a large array of sensors, and the ingress/egress of the optical fiber from the laminate, will be discussed.

KEYWORDS: Fiber Bragg gratings, smart composites

INTRODUCTION

The last ten years have seen an increasing introduction of fiber Bragg grating based load monitoring systems in a broad range of applications. Civil engineering and naval construction are being interesting test platforms previous to the application of this technology in aerospace structures, a field much more conservative to the introduction of emergent technologies.

Despite the early identification of fiber optic based sensing as a promising technology used in combination with advanced composite structures, up to date, most of the work involving fiber optics and, particularly fiber Bragg gratings, has been carried out in very simple applications, and with a low level of structural integration. An immediate consequence of this fact is the reduced number of experiments involving fiber Bragg gratings and composite materials in configurations prone to complex but realistic conditions: fiber Bragg gratings embedded in graphite/epoxy parts cured at high temperature and pressure, in parts of the structure that will be submitted to complex and/or critical loads, that is, submitted to non-uniform or/and non-unidirectional strain and stress fields.

Airbus España, INTA (the Spanish Aerospace Research Center) and UPM (Universidad Politecnica de Madrid) are collaborating in a program directed to increase the experience and the knowledge in the use of fiber Bragg gratings as strain and damage sensors in advanced composite structures, at different levels, that is:

- Progressive substitution of conventional resistive strain gauge extensometry by FBGs, with the consequent elimination of heavy bunches of cables, easier and faster integration, multiplexing capability, long term stability of the measurements and competitive cost per channel are some of the reasons.

- Development of embedding techniques, making fiber optic sensors suitable to be integrated in composite parts manufactured under real manufacturing conditions, including trimming and assembly operations, with a high rate of survivability.
- Demonstration of reliability of the measurements afforded by embedded fiber optic sensors. Up to now, there is little verification of measurements given by embedded fiber optic sensors compared to superficially bonded gauges.
- Analysis of the ability of fiber Bragg gratings to detect damage in damage tolerant structures, detecting changes in the strain-stress fields of structural elements as stringers, stiffeners, etc.
- Several research groups have done important efforts to analyze the behavior of fiber Bragg gratings when submitted to longitudinal non-uniform strain fields, and to decode the strain field applied to the grating by integrating its spectral information (1,2,3).
- Characterization of the response to non-unidirectional stress. A transverse stress field applied to the grating promotes a birefringence that modifies the isotropic optical structure of the fiber, generating two principal directions of polarization, with two different refractive indexes. The fiber Bragg grating verifies two different Bragg conditions, and the optical spectrum of the grating splits in two. The authors of this document have already proposed a model for it (4,5). The model shows a good agreement between experimental results and stresses calculated by the lamination theory.

Fig. 1. Spectra of a fiber Bragg grating bonded in an aluminum beam: unloaded (black) and submitted to a uniform longitudinal strain of 5000 me (gray). The "ideal" behavior of a grating.

Fig. 2. Spectra of a FBG embedded in a unidirectional composite laminate near a bonded joint: unloaded (black) and submitted to longitudinal load (gray). The distortion is due to strain gradients.

Fig 3. Spectra of a FBG before (black) and after being embedded in a thick quasi-isotropic laminate cured in autoclave (gray); the splitted red spectrum shows the effect of strong transverse stresses over the grating.

Fig. 4. Spectra of a FBG embedded in a composite beam made with fabric and cured in autoclave, showing both transversal stresses and non-uniform strain along the grating

This model can be considered a useful tool in multiple applications in which plane stress conditions are expected: thermally induced residual stresses, complex strain and stress fields, etc. In particular, the capability of fiber Bragg gratings to show the thermal residual stresses stored in a composite laminate, and the effect of damage induced residual stress relaxation observed in these materials, opens a new research line in the use of fiber optic sensors as embedded damage sensors in composite structures.

The most immediate result that can be induced from this model is that the distance between the two peaks of the splitted peak is only affected by the transverse stress applied to the fiber, and is proportional to it (figure 5):

Fig. 5. The distance between the two peaks of the splitted peak is only affected by the transverse stress applied to the fiber, and is proportional to it.

Thus, the effect of impact damage in composite laminates has been investigated. A distortion of the spectrum would reflect the progressive relaxation of the residual stresses stored in the material. Fig. 6 shows the intensity spectrum of fiber Bragg gratings embedded in a CFRP panel after 20, 40 and 80 Joules impact, and after the drilling of a 15, 20 and 25 mm diameter hole.

Fig. 6. Intensity spectrum of fiber Bragg gratings before impacts (black, several spectra with energy exchange between lobes are represented), after 20, 40 and 80 Joules impact (in medium gray, with increasing thickness for increasing impact energy), and after the drilling of a 15, 20 and 25 mm diameter hole (in light gray, with increasing thickness for increasing diameter).

This paper summarizes these research lines, presenting some of the results obtained in the last tests carried out.

EXTENSOMETRY WITH FIBRE BRAGG GRATINGS

The use of fiber Bragg gratings bonded in composite structures to replace conventional strain gauges is the most basic application of these sensors, and optical sensors begin to demonstrate that they can compete with resistive gauges with important advantages, even in price. AIRBUS España is starting to introduce this technique in mechanical tests only as a complement of traditional methods. Low profile of optical sensors avoids their utilization in positions not accessible by resistive gauges. Next

image shows, as example, an schematic of a compression test panel with 16 fiber Bragg gratings bonded in different positions. Optical sensors can be bonded, for instance, in the head of the stringers web, a place not accessible for conventional sensors. Results of the test, summarized in figure 8, shows the good correspondence between strain data given by conventional strain gauges and fiber optic sensors.

Fig. 7. Schematic of a compression test panel with 16 FBGs.

Fig. 8. Comparison of results obtained by conventional resistive gauges and FBGs. Differences are due to the position of the FBG, at the head of the stringer.

However, the most interesting results of these kind of test are not reflected on these graphics. A careful analysis of the data acquired by the FBGs allows to obtain interesting results that allow to foresee their use as damage sensors.

Figure 9 shows a premature buckling of the webs of two stiffeners of the panel, still at low level of strain. The decreasing of load absorbed by these stringers is compensated by the increase of load, and subsequent compressive strain in other stringers. Figure 10 shows the progressive failure of the stringers, with different severity.

Fig. 9. Buckling of the webs of two stiffeners of the panel

Fig. 10 Progressive failure of the stringers

However, the behavior shown by the FBG R1 in figure 10 (zoomed in fig. 11) is still more significant. The signal of this grating splits in two due to a spectral distortion, revealing the complex character of these sensors. It is very difficult to identify if this distortion is promoted by a non uniform longitudinal strain, or a spectral splitting due to transverse stresses.

Fig. 11. Splitting of the signal of a FBG, promoted by a spectral distortion

These phenomena, experienced by many authors, result in perturbations in the spectral response of the grating, and affect not only the reliability of the measurement, but even the technique and device use to do it (conventional "peak locators" are useless to give reliable information about the load condition of the specimen, being necessary to obtain the full spectral response of the grating and to have a clear understanding of the problem).

These results are a good introduction to the second step in the introduction of fiber Bragg gratings in composite materials: the use of embedded fibers in stiffened curved structures

Figure 12 Cocured Integrally stiffened curved panels, Cowlings of A 340

BLADE STIFFENED PANELS WITH EMBEDDED FBGS

Three blade-stiffened panels with co-cured stiffener webs were manufactured by means of manual lay-up and autoclave curing. Two embedded optical fiber sensors in each stiffener. Additionally FBGs and strain gauges were bonded on the stiffener webs and on the skin back to back.

The panels have a dimension of 560 mm x 280 mm with 3 blade stiffeners of 20 x 20 mm cross-section situated in the middle line and at 105 mm on the left and on the right from the middle line. Skin thickness is 1 mm and stiffener thickness 1,6 mm. Fiber lay up of the panels has been optimized, being in panel 3 skin: $(\pm 45^\circ_{(f)}, \pm 45^\circ_{(f)}, 0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ_{(f)}, \pm 45^\circ_{(f)})$ and in the stiffener: $(\pm 45^\circ_{(f)}, 0^\circ, 0/90^\circ_{(f)}, 0^\circ)_s$ using a combination of unidirectional and fabric $_{(f)}$ carbon fibers.

Fig.13: Dimensions of the panels with details of the sensors position in panel 1,2 and 3.

For manufacturing the stiffened panels a toughened epoxy prepreg material HEXCEL A-193-P/8552S carbon fabric and AS4/8552 unidirectional tape with AS4 high-strength, high-strain carbon fiber were employed.

The panels were manually laid-up over a reinforced elastomeric mould made of AIRPAD polyacrylic rubber (AIRTECH). The elastomeric mould turned out to be very suitable for embedding the optical fibers in the laminate. The elastic rubber surface of the mould enables the optical fibers covered by their protection tubes to be guided between the laminate and the mould and protects them from high-pressure concentrations (fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Integration of optical fibers in the stiffener webs

Two FBGs were embedded in the web of each one of the three stiffeners of the panel. The optical fibers were placed between the two central 0° layers and parallel to the reinforcement fibers. Their sensing zone was located at mid-span of the stiffener. Embedding the optical fibers between 0° prepreg layers ensures that they will not be destroyed during the consolidation process and that they will provide a reliable sensor signal that will not be spoiled by the lobed curve surface of the fabric layers. A tiny hole was made passing through the laminate to enable the optical fiber to get out of it. A 0.8mm diameter PTFE tube was used to protect and guide the two optical fibers in each web out of the laminate. This tube was sealed with silicone to prevent resin contamination. A lead of about 25mm of this PTFE tube was left inside the laminate to guaranty a good protection of the fiber at the point where it comes out from the laminate. The rest of this PTFE tube was guided between the laminate and the mould coming out of the mould at its front side. A long portion of the protected optical fiber was left outside the laminate and a connector was fixed to it after curing.

Additional FBGs and conventional strain gauges were surface bonded on the panel to verify the strain measurements of the embedded FBGs. Conventional strain gauges were also bonded on the skin to determine the skin buckling. The strain gauges were bonded in all the webs on the left web side at the same location than the upper embedded FBGs is; FBGs were bonded on the right web side. In the middle web also additional gauges were bonded in front of the lower FBGs on both sides of the web.

All the sensors survived the manufacturing of the part, showing clearly defined spectral peaks with no significant distortion due to complex local strain fields caused by residual stresses.

COMPRESSION TEST OF BLADE STIFFENED PANELS

Compression tests at room temperature were conducted for the three panels using for panel 1 and 3 a mechanical testing machine with fixed compression plates and for panels 2 a hydraulic testing machine with bearings allowing longitudinal rotation of the upper plate and transversal rotation of the lower one.

Tests have been conducted up to rupture of panel 1 and 2. Panel 3 has not been loaded up to rupture and several compression tests have been performed.

During the tests, the strains were measured by means of a scanning fiber Bragg grating demodulator developed at the UPM and in case of panel 3 also with an optical spectrum analyzer from the company HP.

In panels 1 and 2 the sensors worked correctly up to the panels failure. In the explosive rupture the splice of the photosensitive and the conventional single-mode fiber broke at almost every sensor. Fixing an optical connector directly to the photosensitive fiber would leave the sensors operative even after rupture of the panel.

Fig. 16: Strain vs. load values from the FBGs and strain gauges of stiffener web 1 and 3 in panel 3

In the case of panel 3 the six FBGs were embedded in the centerline of the stiffener web so that they were able to measure tensile/compression strains but not transversal bending or twisting of the web. At the beginning of the compression test all the sensors detect the same compressive strain up to the moment when buckling occurs at a strain level of $800 \mu\epsilon$. A large bending strain in the skin can be

noticed by the bifurcation of the sensor signals of the bonded strain gauges. Skin buckling increases the load that has to be carried by the stiffeners and induces also a twisting and transverse bending of the stiffeners. With increasing load, longitudinal bending of the web occurs.

Figure 16 shows the strain measured with the upper embedded FBGs, the bonded FBGs and the bonded strain gauge of the stiffener web 1,2 and 3. The measurement of the skin bonded strain gauges is also included in the graph to indicate the skin buckling.

CONCLUSIONS

The use FBGs as strain and damage sensors embedded into composite structures is not an immediate issue. A good knowledge of the sensor-host interaction is needed.

The strain values of the FBGs were compared with the bonded strain gauges. In general a very good agreement of both values could be seen, differing less than $25 \mu\epsilon$ in most of the measurement in the pre-buckling phase. After buckling the values from embedded sensors to surface bonded sensors bifurcate due to the twist of the stiffener. In a case, an appreciable spectral splitting or distortion has been detected.

Further tests with FBGs embedded at the interface between the stiffener web and the skin, in cocured and cobonded parts are been carried out. Both capability of FBGs as simple strain sensors or damage sensors (detecting delamination and debonding of stiffeners will be investigated). In this case, local effects over the spectral response of the gratings will be determinant.

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